

Artist's Impressions in Astronomy and Planetary Science

Philip Corneille
FRAS

Belgium

@PhilipCorneille

Ph.Corneille@Telenet.be

Keywords

Astronomy, engagement, Hubble Space

Telescope, outreach, science communication

Summary

The visual impact of images taken with telescopes like the Hubble Space Telescope is comparable with any of the most beautiful conventional works of art. These images are not only art in their own right, they also inspire space artists to create new pieces of art. This article explores the role of space art in astronomy outreach.

Introduction

Astronomy and space science receive a great deal of attention in the media, fueling public interest. Space agencies and astronomical associations realise the strategic importance of communication and produce press releases. However, the general public often perceive science as difficult and disconnected from everyday life and it remains difficult to stand out in the explosion of online media.

As science communicators we can use the artistic appeal of images to give scientific results more newsworthiness, a broader appeal and, in some cases, to help to better explain the discoveries.

Images from some telescopes, of some objects, can grab headlines by themselves, but when these images are not available, an artist's impression can catch the attention of the media, who more often than not will need a good visual to support a story, no matter how interesting the science.

The history of art and science

Both science and art involve structural representation, imagination and curiosity. These similarities are represented in the work of the great scientists and inventors of the Renaissance. The Italian polymath Leonardo da Vinci (1452–1519) is famous for his beautiful yet scientifically accurate drawings of the human body, animal anatomy and of the machines of his own

invention. As is the Dutch anatomist and physician Andreas Vesalius (1514–1564)¹.

The illustrations of da Vinci and Vesalius were an effective way of recording, publishing and spreading scientific findings to other scholars. Astronomy too has a very long tradition of translating observational data into visual representations in order to leave a record for future generations. Chinese astronomers depicted stars and appearances of comets on oracle bones and ox scapula for millennia².

The history of illustration in astronomy

The introduction of the telescope in 1608 vastly improved astronomical observations. Four centuries later we can compare

the scientific data embedded in early illustrations made before the invention of the telescope with those that came afterwards.

While the informational content in the Moon drawings of Galileo Galilei (1564–1642) was limited to revealing the mountainous topography, the splendid illustrations made by Thomas Harriot (1560–1621) plotted the locations of lunar features precisely, culminating in a cartographic map of the near side of the Moon. As telescopes grew bigger, astronomers such as William Parsons (1800–1867) were able to produce detailed representations of spiral galaxies and planetary nebulae^{3, 4}.

With the advent of astrophotography in the mid-nineteenth century and radio astronomy in the mid-twentieth century it seemed that there might come an end to astronomical sketching. However, new discoveries and beautiful imagery from the telescopes themselves have boosted the creativity of a new generation of space artists.

The modern space artist

In the 1960s, new astronomical discoveries and the emergence of spaceflight inspired illustrators such as the Czech Ludek Pesek (1919–1999), the American Chesley Bonestell (1888–1986) and the Russian Andrei Sokolov (b. 1931). Their paintings, which depict rocket ships, meteors, lunar and Martian landscapes, binary stars and galaxies, strived to show the wonders of the Universe in a different light⁵.

Figure 1. NASA's artist's illustration depicted New Horizons' flyby of the Pluto–Charon system. The icy dwarf planet is covered by a red carbon-rich residue caused by the breakup of solid methane due to ultraviolet radiation from the distant Sun. Credit: NASA

Figure 2. Artist's impression by the Dutch space artist Ed Hengeveld showing the dwarf planet Pluto and its largest moon Charon lit by the faint illumination from a distant Sun. Hengeveld explicitly depicted Pluto as a classic icy small Solar System body. Credit: Philip Corneille/Ed Hengeveld

Space artists have worked closely with scientists to help them visualise scientific concepts and communicate astronomical discoveries to the general public. In 1982, the International Association of Astronomical Artists was founded to bring space artists together⁶. Their creations, from traditional paintings to digital creations, have graced numerous magazine covers, provided movie effects and illustrated scientific articles in a unique manner.

Astronomy illustrations and the media

Since the new millennium, illustrative space art has become an inescapable element of scientific publications and contemporary media. Contemporary artist's impressions make articles aesthetically more appealing and more inviting to read. Artist's impressions are often created to represent concepts and objects that cannot be seen with

the naked eye, that are very big, very small, in the past, in the future, fictional, or otherwise abstract. Herein lies the strength of an illustration, which can give an audience an impression of the nature of hostile objects like pulsars and black holes.

My experience with astronomy illustration

In the winter of 2007, after a decade of illustrating my articles with the well-known drawings created or commissioned by space agencies and observatory press offices, I commissioned the Dutch space artist Ed Hengeveld (b. 1956) to create a few paintings to embellish my articles on the unmanned exploration of the outer Solar System. Hengeveld is famous for his depictions of astronauts on the Moon during the *Apollo* projects of the 1970s, but he also creates artworks on the subject of astronomical discoveries. So, he

seemed to me the obvious choice to illustrate the exciting and distant Pluto–Charon encounter in the Kuiper Belt by NASA's *New Horizons* spacecraft^{7,8}.

As there is no direct observational image of these Trans-Neptunian objects, NASA released an artist's concept, shown in Figure 1, of the spacecraft approaching Pluto and its largest moon Charon⁸. This was based on observations by the Hubble Space Telescope, which showed the red carbon-rich residue left behind as the ultraviolet radiation from the distant Sun broke up methane on Pluto's surface.

I explicitly asked Hengeveld to depict a more classic small astronomical body showing white–brown surface frost, seen in Figure 2. By using both NASA's and Hengeveld's depictions in a single article, readers were encouraged to think about how Pluto might look. Most Kuiper Belt objects may have a reddish colour,

Figure 3. Dutch space artist Ed Hengeveld created an informative artwork full of symbolism to celebrate the 125th anniversary of astronomer Edwin Powell Hubble and the 25th anniversary of the Hubble Space Telescope. Both the astronomer and the eponymous space telescope played an important role in discovering the accelerating expansion of the Universe. Credit: Philip Corneille/Ed Hengeveld

whereas scattered-disc objects, which have more eccentric orbits as a result of gravitational interactions, might look whiter. We will soon know as *New Horizons*, zipping through the outer Solar System at nearly 1.5 million kilometres per day, is due to arrive at Pluto this year.

Illustrations for Edwin Hubble's 125th anniversary and the Hubble Space Telescope's 25th anniversary

In November 2014, the astronomical community celebrated the 125th anniversary of the American astronomer Edwin Powell Hubble (1889–1953) who discovered the expansion of the Universe using the 2.50-metre telescope at Mount Wilson Observatory in California, USA⁹. In April 2015, the Space Telescope Science Institute in Baltimore, USA, together with the European Southern Observatory (ESO) and the American (NASA) and European (ESA) space agencies celebrated 25 years of Hubble's namesake telescope, the Hubble Space Telescope (HST).

I commissioned Ed Hengeveld again to create a painting combining both anniversaries in a single informative artist's impression, shown in Figure 3. The result was an amazing artwork showing the astronomer together with the 2.50-metre telescope and the Hubble Space Telescope observing the spiral Andromeda Galaxy, also known as Messier 31.

Beauty is in the eye of the beholder, but Hengeveld's painting is full of symbolism, and effectively combined history and science in a unique way. The meaning and subject are immediately apparent, crossing language barriers so that the painting can be used to popularise science worldwide.

To commemorate a quarter century of the HST's success in engineering, science and outreach, the general public participated in the celebrations by creating their own Hubble-inspired video artworks. The winning videos from the competition can be found on the ESA/Hubble website¹⁰.

Conclusion

Sharing the wonders of the Universe is one of the most enjoyable and rewarding aspects of astronomy. Moreover, by pairing our natural love of art with exciting science, we can create an engaged public and capture their imaginations. It is one of the most exciting ways of bringing astronomical science closer to the people.

Notes

- ¹ For more information on Leonardo da Vinci and Andreas Vesalius: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Leonardo_da_Vinci
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Andreas_Vesalius
- ² For more information on astronomy in ancient China: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chinese_astronomy
- ³ For more information on selenography and lunar mapping: <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Selenography>
- ⁴ For more information on deep sky observations using large reflectors in the 19th century: <http://www.klima-luft.de/steinicke/ngcic/persons/rosse3.htm>
- ⁵ For more information on space art and a list of space artists: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Space_art
- ⁶ For more information on the International Association of Astro-Artists: <http://iaaa.org/>
- ⁷ For more background on Dutch space artist Ed Hengeveld: <https://www.hq.nasa.gov/alsj/hengeveld.html>
- ⁸ For the latest on NASA's *New Horizons* mission to Pluto-Charon: http://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/newhorizons/main/
- ⁹ For more information on the history of the Mount Wilson Observatory: <http://www.mtwilson.edu/>
- ¹⁰ For more information on 25 years of the Hubble Space Telescope: <https://www.spacetelescope.org/projects/Hubble25/>

Biography

Philip Corneille is an amateur astronomer who works as a distance e-learning & ICT consultant with a keen interest in remote robotic technologies. As a Fellow of the Royal Astronomical Society, he documents the history, telescopes and instruments of professional astronomical observatories. Philip is member of Astronomers Without Borders and so far, he has visited 160 observatories in 33 countries.